

A Proposal of Revision of Floridi’s Conjecture

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Abstract

In response to Luciano Floridi’s conjecture on a fundamental trade-off between certainty and scope in symbolic and generative AI ([Floridi, 2025](#)), we identify formal issues in the original definitions—specifically, the conflation of probabilistic and order-theoretic notions in model correctness (C) and the opaque use of cumulative Kolmogorov complexity for mapping scope (S). Retaining all original philosophical foundations and motivations, we (i) introduce an Epistemic Certainty Level that replaces a mixed supremum–probability measure with a coherent expectation over indicator functions on output space’s equivalence classes; (ii) substitute cumulative Kolmogorov complexity with Shannon joint entropy to better quantify input/output mapping scope and make it more tractable computationally-wise.

Introduction

In “A Conjecture on a Fundamental Trade-Off Between Certainty and Scope in Symbolic and Generative AI,” (Floridi, 2025) the author posits that for every sufficiently expressive AI mechanism M , there exists a constant $k > 0$ such that¹:

$$\exists k: C(M)S(M) \leq k$$

where $C(M)$ captures worst-case correctness and $S(M)$ denotes the cumulative Kolmogorov complexity of the input and output spaces. We think that despite its insightful aims, the original presentation exhibits two key issues:

1. Definition of C conflates the supremum (least upper bound) with a probabilistic expectation, yielding a mixed semantics that hinders formal clarity.
2. Kolmogorov complexity of a space is stated without reference to a precise formalism for aggregating the complexity of multiple objects or spaces.

¹ The original formulation published in (Floridi, 2025) had a material error in the conjecture formulation that the author subsequently fixed in (Floridi, 2025-2).

We therefore elaborate alternative formulations that preserve the original motivations and mathematical relationships while resolving these issues.

Epistemic Certainty Level

Floridi's original correctness measure C is informally described via a supremum over probabilistic constraints, effectively merging the order-theoretic concept of a least upper bound with statistical confidence intervals. The original formulation is as follows:

$$C(M) = 1 - \sup_{x \in I} P(f_M(x) \neq Spec(x))$$

Where I is the input set of the AI mechanism M , $f_M(x)$ is its input-output mapping function and $Spec(x)$ is the true (expected) output. The interpretation of this formula is that the correctness is eroded by the supremum of the probability distribution of the random variable representing the ability of M to produce correct outputs. However, in general, such a distribution may have a supremum value that is occasionally very high because of a few input x and much lower for the rest of the domain. Furthermore, these toxic inputs may be associated with very low probability of occurrence. Another issue is related to the inherent strong assumption that the outputs of the mechanism can be always sharply assessed (through inequality) as being correct or incorrect w.r.t. their inputs or – in other terms – that there exist one and only one possible correct output for each input.

This situation will end up on the one hand in strongly underestimating C in most concrete cases and on the other hand to overlook the user-dependent judgement. To disentangle these issues, we firstly define:

$$C_u(M) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim P(x)}(1\{f_M(x) \approx Spec_u(x)\})$$

where:

- \mathbb{E} denotes the expected value of a random variable;
- $1\{\}$ is the indicator function, i.e. 1 when its argument is true and 0 otherwise;
- \approx induces an equivalence relation on the set of acceptable outputs for a user u .

We call this reformulation User-centric Epistemic Certainty Level. There are some notable improvements introduced by this formulation: firstly, inputs are weighted according to their probability of occurrence. Secondly, we take the expected value of the phenomenon constituted by the observation of a correct output. Lastly, we use the approximation inequality to extend the notion of exact identity towards the notion of equivalence. This latter element deserves a further explanation: in practical cases, the correctness of a certain output cannot be stated with precision, but rather a set of possible answers can be considered equivalent to the expected ground truth from the point of view of the observing user. In more formal terms, each input to the mechanism induces a partition of the output space in two separate equivalence classes, and this partition is user-dependent.

In total, this Epistemic Certainty Level cleanly separates deterministic ordering from stochastic averaging, while accommodating user-dependent notions of correctness.

As a natural extension of this approach we take into consideration the fact that different users (in the space U of users) may have different ideas about the correctness of a response given x , yielding to a higher order formulations of C – the Epistemic Certainty Level:

$$C(M) = \mathbb{E}_{u \sim P(u)} C_u = \mathbb{E}_{u \sim P(u)} (\mathbb{E}_{x \sim P(x)} (1\{M(x) \approx Spec_u(x)\}))$$

thereby preserving the original intent of capturing variability in user judgments.

Joint Entropy

In the original formulation of the conjecture, the mapping scope $S(M)$ is defined as the summation of the Kolmogorov complexity of the input and output spaces:

$$S(M) = K(I) + K(O)$$

It has to be noticed that Kolmogorov complexity $K(s)$ of a finite string s is the length of the shortest program that outputs s on a fixed universal Turing machine. Floridi's proposal to apply this notion to a space lacks a clear protocol for summation/weighting over the space and overlooks completeness, representativeness and intractability concerns. In fact, to properly estimate the mapping scope in this form one should be able to traverse the entire input space and collect all corresponding outputs and then calculate all Kolmogorov complexities.

To overcome these limits, we propose Shannon entropy (Shannon, 1948) as a principled measure of mapping scope:

$$S(M) = H(I) + H(O) = - \left(\sum_{x \in I} P(x) \log(P(x)) + \sum_{x \in O} P(x) \log(P(x)) \right)$$

This first attempt, however, does not take into consideration the fact that inputs and outputs values (x, y) are not independent variables, but they are liaised by the joint probability $P(x, y)$.

We then refine the proposal by employing the joint entropy:

$$S(M) = H(I, O) = - \sum_{x, y \in I \times O} P(x, y) \log(P(x, y))$$

capturing correlations between inputs and outputs and leveraging a computable information-theoretic framework. Thus, through this replacement, the initial formulation – which required a deterministic exploration of the input-output mapping function $f_M(x)$, is

transformed in a probabilistic problem, which can be approached via robust and more tractable statistical analysis.

Reformulated Conjecture

With these revised definitions, the conjecture assumes the following form:

There exists a constant $k > 0$, independent of any specific system M , such that every sufficiently expressive AI mechanism M satisfies:

$$S(M)C(M) \leq k$$

where $C(M)$ is the Epistemic Certainty Level and $S(M)$ is the Joint Entropy of the input and output spaces.

Conclusion

By preserving its original motivations and the philosophical and epistemological foundations of Floridi's conjecture, our formal refinements of the mathematical formulations resolve some core issues of the proposed mathematical concepts and anchor the trade-off between certainty and scope in rigorous, computable measures. We believe the proposed reformulations are more tractable in practice, so that future work may explore empirical validation of the constant k across symbolic and generative AI architectures, and extend the framework to continuous or high-dimensional domains.

References

1. Floridi, L. A Conjecture on a Fundamental Trade-Off Between Certainty and Scope in Symbolic and Generative AI. *Philosophy and Technology* 38, 1–11 (2025).
2. Floridi, L, A Conjecture on a Fundamental Trade-off between Certainty and Scope in Symbolic and Generative AI (June 11, 2025). Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5289884>
3. Shannon, C. "A Mathematical Theory of Communication," *Bell System Technical Journal* 27, 379–423 (1948).
4. Cover, T. M. & Thomas, J. A. *Elements of Information Theory*. Wiley-Interscience (2006).

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